

Hazard assessment of the agrochemical contaminant desnitro-imidacloprid (DN-IMI) for developmental neurotoxicity (DNT)

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Disclaimer: Information was entered in ASPA-assist, with the objective to showcase the workflow, and to exemplify relevant uses of data and approaches. Completeness in a technical, regulatory and scientific sense was not the primary goal. **Conclusive coverage of all aspects has been actively avoided to limit the size of the document and to facilitate an easy overview.** *At pivotal decision points or data summaries, notes were inserted (in italics) that are meant to enhance the illustrative character of this case study. They indicate options and recommendations for best practices when ASPA is used for other than demonstration purposes.*

Report objective: **Exemplification** of ASPA-assist V2.1 (performed on 10. Feb 2026; updated on 08. April 2026).

ASPA overview: A high-resolution version of the below workflow (ASPA V2.1) is found on the large page of this file (note that the size is much larger than normal A4 page sizes to enhance readability)

Executive summary

Desnitro-imidacloprid (DN-IMI) was used as query compound to showcase the workflow designed for an *ab initio* next-generation risk assessment (NGRA). **The problem formulation specified as data gap to be addressed: developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) for consumers exposed via contaminated food.** The exposure calculations were anchored to data on food residue levels available for the parent compound imidacloprid. This neonicotinoid pesticide, in widespread use in many non-European countries, forms the environmental metabolite DN-IMI within crops and soil. It was assumed that DN-IMI levels were up to about 2 % of imidacloprid residues. In three exposure scenarios (ES1 (worst case), ES2 and ES3 (European consumer), the E_{\max} for DN-IMI was assumed to be **1.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$ – 0.012 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$** . In particular ES3 refers to real consumption data (from the European Union).

DN-IMI was predicted to be water-soluble, orally absorbed (100%), brain-penetrant, and predominantly cleared renally, with negligible hepatic metabolism, making it suitable for NAM-based testing and PBK modelling. PBK simulations for pregnant women and their fetuses predicted peak fetal brain concentrations around 8 nM ($\pm \sim 40\%$).

QSAR, followed by docking approaches, identified the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) as relevant molecular initiating event. The relevance of the associated AOP was judged high, as nicotine, a known DNT toxicant, is known to trigger the same MIE. The potency of target interaction was experimentally determined by neuronal Ca^{2+} imaging and electrophysiology. The most relevant PoD for adversity was defined as 0.1 μM (nAChR overactivation; CI 30–300 nM), with receptor desensitization at 0.01 μM considered supportive, but less well linked to apical DNT. An in vitro-to-in vivo extrapolation of this yielded a human equivalent dose (HED) of **20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$** .

Broad screening (up to 100 μM) showed no additional hazards. A comparison of the PoD (100 nM $\pm 30\%$) with modeled fetal brain levels (internal exposure) at the highest exposure yielded an internal bioactivity–exposure ratio (iBER) of about 12.7 (ES1), 31 (ES2) and about 1700 (ES3). These numbers correspond numerically also to the respective margins-of-exposure (MoEs). For exiting and report finalization, it is suggested to address the major uncertainties of this assessment (in particular the exposure assumption and the modelling of brain levels) before coming to a definite risk assessment decision.

Graphical abstract

Graphical abstract: ASPA case study on desnitro-imidacloprid (DN-IMI)

The exposure pillar (right, blue) uses data on imidacloprid (IMI) as input. The IMI residues present in food are assumed to contain 2% DN-IMI. Based on this, three exposure scenarios (ES1-ES3) have been chosen, and the respective maximal exposures (E_{max}) are indicated. The hazard pillar (left, orange) uses DN-IMI as input. The computational approaches (e.g. quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSAR)) identified the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) as likely target. Based on this, DN-IMI was assumed to act similar to nicotine by activating an AOP leading from its molecular initiating event (MIE: nAChR) to the adverse outcome (AO: developmental neurotoxicity (DNT)). Screening in an extensive NAM battery identified the nAChR as most relevant and sensitive target, with a calculated point-of-departure (PoD) of 100 nM. The physiology-based kinetic (PBK) model, developed in the ADME pillar (bottom, green) was used in an in vitro-to-in vivo procedure to derive the human equivalent dose (HED) from the PoD. The PBK model was also used to derive C_{max} concentrations for fetal and adult brains for the three exposure scenarios (ESx). These were used (middle, grey) to calculate internal bioactivity-exposure ratios (iBER). Note that these iBER are numerically equivalent to the margins of exposure (MoE). This information was then recommended as basis for a potential risk assessment, which would incorporate an uncertainty analysis and comprehensive reporting on the basis of the structure and data provided in ASPA2.1 format. The study partially uses information from an earlier IATA case study (OECD, 2022)

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1. General information

1.2 Substance

- *Name*: Desnitro-imidacloprid
- *Casrn*: 115970-17-7
- *ID*: dtxcid:DTXCID60386837, dtxsid:DTXSID90436011, pubchemcid:10130527

1.2 General description

DN-IMI was selected for this demonstration, as legacy data from the public domain could be used. DN-IMI may be formed in crops from the neonicotinoid pesticide imidacloprid and thus, consumers may be exposed to DN-IMI via food. The compound as such is not in commercial use. ASPA-assist was used as a tool to present and sort the available data.

As many decision points in ASPA depend on the problem formulation, a demonstration study on ASPA requires the simulation of a real-life setting. For this purpose, the problem formulation stipulates that **the DNT concern of DN-IMI be closer investigated. Therefore, the specific objective of the evaluation is a potential DNT concern (as may be tested for pesticides according to OECD TG 426 (OECD, 2007)), other endpoints (and their respective testing objectives and guidelines) are not considered here.**

It was asked whether a next-generation risk assessment (NGRA) approach, represented by ASPA, may provide information on (i) what is the relevant range of target site concentrations and cognate exposures that leads to an adverse outcome in humans, (ii) and how does this compare to internal and external exposures, e.g. in the European population.

1.3 Background

The neonicotinoid imidacloprid is metabolized in plants. Desnitro-imidacloprid (DN-IMI) can be formed during this process. Therefore, DN-IMI may be taken up in plant-based food.

DN-IMI is structurally related to nicotine, a known DNT toxicant. Nicotine is assumed to act via activation of the nAChR. It is not known whether DN-IMI may show a toxicity similar to nicotine.

1.4 Regulatory framework

Assessment of environmental chemicals that may be present in food. It is **not about evaluating a pesticide product or active ingredient**, but **refers to potential contaminants or secondary products**. The potential formation of DN-IMI from imidacloprid by human metabolism was not considered here, as the data on this are ambiguous. Relevant stakeholders would be agencies dealing with food safety, such as EFSA (Europe), the FDA (USA), or the BfR (Germany). The regulation guiding these exemplary agencies and many others in the world differ. In general, they all aspire to determine an exposure or a respective experimental dose that marks the threshold between no (adverse) effect and toxicity. This aligns with the main goal of this study.

1.5 Endpoints

DNT hazard assessment; Estimates on the likely bioactivity exposure relationships (BER) in “normal consumers, living in countries with non-prohibited use of imidacloprid (e.g. Europe in 2012 or Brazil nowadays).

2. Generic part (ASPA entry)

Note: The full overview scheme of ASPA V2.1 is found in the attachment of (Leist et al., 2026). This file is conveniently found together with the annexes in one collective folder (see for doi in the references chapter)

2.1 Problem formulation (BB001_01)

2.1.1 Purpose of assessment

An **assessment for a DNT hazard** should be performed to assess the bioactivity exposure relationship of DN-IMI. Focus is given in this workflow to toxicologically-relevant bioactivities and their comparison to internal exposures at relevant target sites. The regulatory framework is the assessment of environmental chemicals that may be present in food (not evaluating a pesticide product or active ingredient).

Uncertainties that will need to be accounted for arise from the assumption that nicotine acts mainly via the activation of the nAChR and that this is closely linked to a DNT effect. Further uncertainties arise through the *in-vitro* assays where each assay has its own intrinsic uncertainty. As in all NGRA approaches, the physiology-based kinetic model (PBK model) used has uncertainties, concerning input parameters and model setup. For instance, the metabolism, barrier passage and solubility of the compound in various compartments play important roles. If an exposure range is available this increases the uncertainty in concordance with the range. A similar consideration has to be taken into account when comparing various point-of-departures (PoDs) from different assays for the BER calculation.

2.1.2 Substance definition

DN-IMI is a metabolite of the neonicotinoid pesticide imidacloprid. It has a molecular weight of 210.66 g/mol. DN-IMI was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich with a purity of 99.7%, and a quality level of 100 according to ISO 9001. Its melting point is at 170.93 °C (degradation). The lot has a residual solvent level of 0.2% ethanol. Water solubility as calculated from the K_{ow} is 68.13 (mg/L) [~ 200 μ M]. There is always an uncertainty on such predictions (e.g. an experimentally assessed water solubility may be higher) and this would affect the PBK model.

2.1.3 Exposure scenarios

Neonicotinoids are mainly used as pesticides. The compounds and their metabolites may remain in the environment and are taken up mainly through the oral route as a food contaminant. The population addressed is the end-consumer. Due to various uses of imidacloprid over time and in different countries, exposures vary considerably between Europeans 2005 or 2025, or between Europeans, Brazilians and Chinese. Here, three exemplary exposure scenarios (ES1, ES2, ES3) have been defined; all are based on assumed imidacloprid (parent compound) exposures.

2.1.4 Need for mechanistic understanding

Mechanistic understanding is a fundamental principle of NGRA, and it is therefore most likely required. Mechanistic information is the basis for data plausibility and also is an important precondition to translate data from model systems to the human population. An exception is perceivable only if there is a very big margin of exposure. This means that hazard is extremely unlikely, even with all uncertainties considered. In this latter situation of a ‘non-hazard’, mechanistic information would be obsolete.

Considering the problem formulation, specific key neurodevelopmental endpoints (e.g., migration, neurite outgrowth, neural network formation and function, cell activation & stimulation) for DNT should be tested to evaluate the DNT hazard and to give a rough risk estimate for exposed populations. Assuming that the mode of action of DN-IMI is similar to that of nicotine, then DN-IMI exerts its effect via the activation of the nAChR. Based on this mechanistic background, specific test methods should be used that give information on nAChR activation. Furthermore, the ‘mechanistic question’ should be addressed, whether DNT-relevant effects occur at concentrations below those causing maternal toxicity. To answer this, a broad panel of potential effects should be screened, and general cytotoxicity data (in several cell lines, covering various organs) should be generated to cover potential organ toxicities.

The ASPA can be exited, when sufficiently detailed information has been generated to fill the knowledge gaps concerning the mode of action (MoA) of DN-IMI, its potency on the nAChR. An early exit would only be possible, if clear evidence for or against a DNT effect has been provided.

2.2 Are there relevant existing data for the substance of interest? (BB002_01)

2.2.1 Summary

In alignment with the scope of this study, it was decided to ignore existing hazard data and to consider this case study mainly as an ab initio evaluation. Note that existing data and models have been for the prediction of internal exposures.

2.2.2 Result

In the context of RiskHunt3R, this case study was designed to address data gaps in DNT evaluation. The substance was selected because its structure indicates a potential hazard. Some published data (ignored here) indicate a mode of action that may be of toxicological relevance. In this case study we decided to use an ab initio hazard evaluation approach existing hazard data for the evaluation and assessment of DN-IMI were ignored. A PBK model developed earlier (OECD 2022), information on exposure to imidacloprid and information on the conversion of imidacloprid to DN-IMI were used here. A document on this background data (BB002_data.pdf) is found in annex II.

2.3 Is the available information sufficient for an assessment? (DP01EF_01)

2.3.1 Summary

As it was assumed for this case study that hazard data are not available, data were considered ‘not sufficient’.

DECISION: NO

2.3.2 Justification

Data available (none) were not considered sufficient to fill knowledge gaps, which were specified in 2.1

2.4 Is read-across applicable? (DP02EF_01)

2.4.1 Summary

For the purpose of this case study (ab initio), read-across was considered not applicable.

DECISION: NO

2.4.2 Justification

Note: For compounds with a potentially high bioactivity (here: DN-IMI), and with specific targets of toxicity (nAChR), a structure based read-across is difficult because of sharp activity cliffs. However, for an overall judgment, information from similarly acting compounds (same target) may be used in the risk assessment part to support plausibility of the overall evaluation.

2.5 Identify data gap(s) and testing strategy, based on problem formulation (BB040_01)

2.5.1 Summary

As available data cannot be used to fill the hazard data gap (DNT hazard) a complete next generation risk assessment (NGRA) evaluation along ASPA is required. As detailed in the hazard pillar (chapter 3), **broad bioactivity and specific neurotoxicity assays are required**. The **toxicokinetics** behavior needs evaluation (chapter 4) to determine internal bioactivity-exposure ratios (iBERs). Relevant **exposure estimates** are required (chapter 5), even though they can use available information on imidacloprid.

2.5.2 Result

The data availability on the bioactivity of DN-IMI is scarce. Therefore, several NAM approaches should be employed to characterize its bioactivity. As the data gap to be filled concerns a potential DNT hazard, specific test batteries for developmental neurotoxicity and additional assays for functional neurotoxicity and signaling should be used for bioactivity characterization. ADME behavior needs to be modelled on the basis of predicted or measured parameters. Through PBK modelling (including the fetal compartments), a dose for different compartments should be derived from the PoDs from the NAMs. Various exposure estimates may be used to generate BER predictions.

2.6 Is NAM -based testing feasible for the substance of interest? (DP04EF_01)

2.6.1 Summary

DN-IMI is **suitable for a NAM-based assessment**, as far as its physico-chemical properties are concerned (see 3.1)

DECISION: YES

2.6.2 Justification

Predictions indicate that DN-IMI is:

- water soluble,

- has very low evaporation (Henry's constant; evaporation coefficient from aqueous solutions), and oral uptake is possible.
- It is a druggable substance according to Lipinski's rule.
- The molecular weight is below 500 g/mol and
- It has a high chemical stability.
- It is likely to penetrate cell membranes and cell-based barriers

3. Hazard

3.1 Generate toxicologically-relevant in silico predictions (BB010_01)

3.1.1 Summary

The (Q)SAR predictions showed no activity for DN-IMI for different nuclear receptors/thyroid function/endocrine disruption. There was **a flag for genotoxicity, but not for acute local toxicities**. Further, **a positive alert was generated for the nAChR and a DNT hazard**. Follow up of the nAChR alert by docking studies showed that the molecular initiating event (MIE) (binding to the nAChR) is likely to happen for several neonicotinoids and their metabolites, including DN-IMI. The alerts suggest that specific DNT related NAMs should be used, since the nAChR is a receptor crucial in development. Potential genotoxicity may require a separate follow-up.

3.1.2 Results

3.1.2.1 Structure based alerts and QSAR

To generate toxicologically relevant predictions, several platforms that provide in-silico tool collections have been utilized. The results from various prediction tools are all available in [Annex I](#). A high-level overview is given in [Table 1](#). Displayed data have been selected for their relevance to the assessment. Data that were unclear, ambiguous or out of the prediction domain have usually not been included. Also, negative data has usually not been selected, with exception for some that have importance for assessment decision points.

The first block of data addresses general test compound behavior: It suggests good oral absorption, and properties of a drug-like compound (sufficient solubility and stability). No significant alerts for interaction with CYPs are given. A low blood-brain ratio is predicted, but no active export from brain by p-glycoprotein.

The second block of predictions addressed typical toxicities/adverse outcomes: There was no alert for local toxicities or carcinogenicity. Environmental toxicity (algae) was alerted in the very low μM range. The oral acute toxicity was determined experimentally and was moderate: it ranged from 130-170 mg/kg (mouse) to about 300 mg/kg (rat) ([see annex II: DN-IMI_BB002_data.pdf](#)).

The third block of predictions addressed genotoxicity: various bacterial and mammalian (Ames test, Comet assay) predictors gave inconclusive predictions out of domain, while the in vivo and in vitro micronucleus predictions gave a positive result. This calls for further clarification! (Background note: *DN-IMI has been tested experimentally in the Ames assay: negative result* ([see annex II: DN-IMI_BB002_data.pdf](#)).

The fourth block of tools addressed potential targets of toxicity: While there was little evidence for most known targets (including endocrine), there was an alert for hERG inhibition (although at high concentrations) and for interaction with the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR). The latter alert came from the SEA tool (based on the ChEMBL database; based on several hits) and was confirmed by a QSAR tool provided via UPF (Barcelona) within the ASPA-assist program. This target was considered important for in vitro testing follow-up.

The various platforms consulted, the method details used by the various tools, validation data and performance standards are indicated or referenced in Annex I, (see also [QSAR general methods supplement.pdf](#)).

Desnitro-Imidacloprid (MW 210; CAS: 115970-17-7)				
Information type	Prediction of	Prediction	Detail	Source
ADME background				
Oral absorption	Bioavailability (according to Lipinski's rule of five score)	high	-	DTU
Oral absorption	GI absorption	high	-	Swiss ADME
Brain/blood distribution	Log brain/blood partition coefficient	poor permeability	-	OECD TB (DTU)
Transport	P-gp substrate	No	-	Swiss ADME
Metabolism	CYP inhibition	1A2/2C19/2C9/2D6/3A4	No	Swiss ADME
Protein reactivity	OECD Toolbox profiler: OASIS, Alerts in (parent only)	no alert	no alert	OECD TB (DTU)
Protein reactivity	OECD Toolbox profiler: OASIS, Alerts in (metabolites from skin metabolism simulator)	no alert	no alert	OECD TB (DTU)
Bioconcentration	Ecotox BCF	3.2	-	EpiSuite (DTU)
AO/toxicity				
Aquatic (Fish)	LC50 for Most Toxic Class in mg/L (96 h)	6.7	-	ECOSAR (DTU)
Algae -acute toxicity (96 h)	ERC50 v1.0.1 in mg/L	174	-	ECOSAR (DTU)
Skin (rabbit, guinea pig, rat)	LLNA & other	no alert	-	
Human: DART	Teratogenic potential	NEG_OUT	-	DTU
Carcinogenicity (rodent)	FDA RCA Cancer	INC_OUT	-	DTU
Carcinogenicity (rat or mouse)	Liver specific cancer	INC_OUT	-	DTU
Genotoxicity				
Bacterial mutations	Ames test in <i>S. typhimurium</i> (in vitro)	INC_OUT	-	DTU
Bacterial mutations	Ames test alerts by ISS (parent only)	no alert	-	OECD TB (DTU)
Mammalian mutations	Mutations in HGPRT locus in CHO cells	INC_OUT	-	DTU
Mammalian clastogenicity	Micronucleus test in erythrocytes (mouse)	INC_OUT	-	DTU
Mammalian clastogenicity	Comet assay (mouse)	INC_OUT	-	DTU
Mammalian clastogenicity	Micronucleus in vitro (VERMEER) v1.0.1	POS_low_Out	-	VEGA (DTU)
In vivo genotoxicity	In vivo micronucleus alerts by ISS (parent only)	POS (alert H-acceptor-path3-H-acceptor)	-	OECD TB (DTU)
MIE/target				
Neurotoxicity	AChE inhibition-in vitro	NEG_IN	sens 94%	DTU
Cardiotoxicity	hERG inhibition (10 µM)	POS	78% positive	ADMETlab3
Various NR/thyroid/ED	Aromatase, AhR, CAR, PXR, PPAR, RAR, NIS, TPO	no alert	-	
Various NR/thyroid/ED	Estrogen receptor (ER) binding, alerts (parent only)	Non binder	Non-binder	OECD TB (DTU)
Various NR/thyroid/ED	ER binding, alerts on simulated rat metabolites	no alert	-	OECD TB (DTU)
SEA alerts	nAChR	several alerts	-	SEA

Table 1: Overview of QSAR predictions (full details in Annex I): The structure of DN-IMI was used as query input to obtain QSAR predictions from several repositories/platforms (indicated as source). A representative sub-selection of the predictions is presented, sorted according to the type of information provided. In the DTU data base (main focus here), a call can be made as positive (POS), negative (NEG), or inconclusive; moreover, information is provided on whether the query compound is 'IN' or 'OUT' of the applicability domain. For models based on regression models, sometimes quantitative data were available (units are indicated). Some models provided prediction probabilities (indicated; C = confidence level). Some models gave as output 'alert' or 'no alert'. Background data, details and model explanation are found in [supplementary information Annex I](#). Most model information is available from the international QSAR model reporting format (QMRF) files at the Danish (Q)SAR database (<https://qsar.food.dtu.dk>), abbreviated here as DTU. Oasis, VEGA and Case Ultra (CU) are database data provided via DTU. The documentation for the hERG inhibition model is available at ADMETlab3 (<https://admetlab3.scbdd.com>). SwissADME data were from <https://www.swissadme.ch/>

AChE: acetylcholine esterase; AhR: aryl hydrocarbon receptor; BCF: bioconcentration factor; CAR: constitutive androstane receptor; CYP: cytochrome P; DART: developmental and reproductive toxicity; GI: gastro-intestinal; hERG: human ether-a-go-go related gene; ISS: Istituto superiore di sanita; LD50/LC50: lethal dose/concentration 50; LLNA: local lymph node

assay; NR: nuclear receptor; NIS: sodium iodide symporter; PPAR γ : peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma; PXR: pregnane X receptor; P-gp: P-glycoprotein; RAR: retinoic acid receptor; RCA: rodent carcinogenicity assessment/alert carcinogens data base; SEA:; similarity ensemble approach; TPO: thyroid peroxidase.

3.1.2.2 Docking studies

In-silico docking studies were used to follow-up on the binding to the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) alert from QSAR (3.1.2.2), as this was considered of very high toxicological relevance. Modulation of acetylcholine receptor activity has hundreds of well-known pharmacological effects, and many toxins affect this group of receptors. Binding to nAChR is an MIE for an AOP. Therefore, docking studies were performed to calculate binding energies and to increase the plausibility for DN-IMI affecting this MIE. Binding energies for DN-IMI, nicotine, and imidacloprid are shown in Table 2 in Annex I. Binding poses for DN-IMI at the $\alpha 7$ nAChR are shown in figure 2.

Figure 1 Binding pose of DN-IMI for the $\alpha 7$ nAChR. DN-IMI is shown in blue carbon atoms, while yellow carbon atoms show the binding pose for IMI.

Supporting documents in subfolder B010_01 in Annex I

- UPF QSAR database predictions DN-IMI.xlsx;
- RH3R AchE DNT 32 predresult NeoNics only :
RH3R_AchE_DNT_32_predresult_NeoNics only.xlsx;
- Molecular docking studies of DN-IMI.pdf;
- QSAR predictions overview DN-IMI;
- DN-IMI_ADMETlab3_result-2.pdf;
- DN-IMI_swissadme.csv;
- DNI-IMI_QSAR.food.dtu.dk_115970-17-7.pdf;
- DN-IMI SEA results.xlsx
- QSAR data handling_V1.pdf
- QSAR Figure DN-IMI.xlsx

3.2 Is there a reason to enter a module for testing specific toxicological endpoints outside core ASPA focus? (DP09EF_01)

3.2.1 Summary

There was no alert for skin sensitization, or topical toxicity. There was an alert for cardiac toxicity (QSAR prediction on hERG). Core ASPA was continued with a focus on developmental neurotoxicity.

DECISION: NO

3.2.2. Justification

No QSAR alert for skin sensitization or acute topical toxicity. An alert was generated for genotoxicity: while this may be clarified (in parallel or later), ASPA was continued to closer investigate a potential DNT hazard. It was decided that knowledge on DNT was relevant, independent of the genotoxicity hazard (which may be confirmed or not). (Background note, see annex I: *DN-IMI has been tested experimentally in the Ames assay: negative result*).

There was an alert for cardiac toxicity (QSAR prediction on hERG). This was not followed here, based on the problem formulation (focus on DNT). Using information from the exposure and ADME pillars, predicting low nM concentrations (or less) of DN-IMI in humans, an effect on hERG was considered unlikely. In other contexts, e.g. evaluation of the general safety of a drug candidate, this alert may have been followed.

3.3 Identify bioactivity (BB011_02)

3.3.1 Cytotoxicity

3.3.2.1 Cytotoxicity summary

DN-IMI shows very low cytotoxicity. Many cell types (including human neurons) remain unaffected at concentrations up to 100 μM (exposure time up to 72 h). The upper test concentrations chosen here do exceed the expected human internal exposure (brain or plasma concentrations) by at least 100-fold (see chapters 4/5).

3.3.2.2 Cytotoxicity results

Cytotoxicity in several cell lines has been investigated to identify specific organ toxicity. For kidney, a resazurin reduction assay in RPTEC cells showed no cytotoxic effect of DN-IMI up to the highest tested concentration of 20 μM (Figure 2). Cytotoxicity assays in immature and mature LUHMES neurons show no effect up to the highest tested concentration of 100 μM (Figure 3). The same (absence of cytotoxicity at concentrations up to 100 μM) was observed for peripheral human neurons and neural crest cells.

Figure 2 Concentration response of DN-IMI measured by resazurin reduction in RPTEC. A value of 100% means 'completely viable and metabolically active cells'

Figure 4 Concentration response of DN-IMI measured in the UKN4 assay. Methods and assay principles are found in detail in Blum et al, 2023 (PMID 36328314). In brief, Human LUHMES neurons were exposed for 24 h, before their viability (cytotoxicity) was measured. In parallel, a functional assay was performed to assess test compound effects on neurite growth (neurite area). The experiments were repeated three times independently, and the variation of separate runs is shown by the error bars.

Data are represented relative to solvent controls. Narciclasine (50 nM) was used in each assay as positive control and fulfilled the acceptance criteria

3.3.2 General bioactivity screening

3.3.2.1 Summary of general bioactivity screening

The DNT-IVB, a test battery dedicated to the identification of DNT hazard has been used. Several assays use highly complex and sensitive cell cultures to provide functional endpoints. None of the assays reacted to DN-IMI at screen concentrations up to 100 µM. Thus, DN-IMI does not affect the key neurodevelopmental processes covered by the DNT-IVB. Moreover, it can be indirectly concluded that the compound did not trigger damage to mitochondria, the cytoskeleton, the proteasome function and several other processes that are sensitively detected by the DNT-IVB.

A broader bioactivity screen may have identified some alerts. Such an activity may still be important as follow-up. The decision will be taken at a later stage. The immediate follow-up will concentrate on the biggest testing gap: none of the screen assays used identified modulation of nAChR activity, which nAChR has been suggested as potential target by in silico approaches. To address this gap, experimental assays for nAChR will be used. Depending on the results (in particular on the potency information from such assays, it will be decided whether more testing is required to identify a potentially more sensitive additional target.

3.3.2.2 Results of general bioactivity screening

According to the problem formulation, a DNT specialized test battery was used here for screening purposes. The so-called 'DNT-IVB' was described in detail earlier, is fully documented in ToxTemps and has an acceptable readiness level, as it has been covered by the OECD GD377. These assays cover most key neurodevelopmental processes (KNDPs) and the DNT-IVB has shown to have good accuracy when challenged with a library of known positive and negative DNT chemicals.

Here, the test compound did not give a relevant alert. This may appear astonishing, but it is consistent with the findings that also nicotine (established as DNT toxicant) did not give alerts. Neither did related compounds, such as acetamiprid and imidacloprid (Blum et al., 2023). Such compounds have very specific, receptor mediated effects, and the test systems used for the DNT-IVB do neither express such receptors. Some cells express the receptor, but the respective assay endpoints are not dependent on this receptor. Two examples of this are given below.

In the neurite outgrowth assays (UKN4 and UKN5), DN-IMI did not show a toxic effect at concentrations up to 100 μM (Figure 4 illustrates the data for UKN4). The cells used for these assays do not express nAChR, so that it is plausible (consistent) that no effect was observed. The assays have been thoroughly characterized not just for the performance, but also for the pathways that lead to a change in the assay endpoint (GD377 and Blum et al, 2023). The UKN4 and UKN5 assays capture effects on the cytoskeleton, mitochondria, various signaling kinases (MAPK, ROCK), the proteasome, protein synthesis, and histone deacetylases. As DN-IMI had no effect on these assays, these processes are likely not affected by the test compound.

In the neurite outgrowth assays (UKN4 and UKN5), DN-IMI did not show a toxic effect at concentrations up to 100 μM (Figure 5 illustrates the data for UKN2).

Figure 3 Concentration response of DN-IMI in the neural crest cell migration assay (UKN2). Methods and assay principles are found in detail in Blum et al, 2023 (PMID 36328314). In brief, human neural crest cells (generated from pluripotent stem cells) were exposed for 24 h, before their viability (cytotoxicity) was measured. In parallel, a functional assay was performed to assess test compound effects on the migration of the cells within a cell culture dish. The experiments were repeated three times independently, and the variation of separate runs is shown by the error bars. Data are represented relative to solvent controls. Cytochalasin D (200 nM) was used in each assay as positive control and fulfilled the

acceptance criteria

The assay (UKN2) has been thoroughly characterized not just for the performance, but also for the pathways that lead to a change in the assay endpoint (GD377 and Blum et al, 2023). The UKN2 assay captures test compound effects on the dynamics of the cytoskeleton (e.g. actin reorganization and the dynamic instability of microtubules at the leading edge), on mitochondria, and on oxidative stress. It is one of the DNT-IVB assays with the highest hit rate, as migration is very sensitive to disturbances of the cell biology. Although the assay detected many diverse compounds, comprising flame retardants, polychlorinated biphenyls, and various metal toxicants, DN-IMI showed no effect. This suggests that the cell biological effects detected sensitively by the phenotypic UKN2 assay are not disturbed by DN-IMI.

3.3.3 Assessment of potential additional targets and maternal toxicity

3.3.3.1 Summary of other bioactivities

Several broad bioactivity screens have been performed. Detailed data evaluation is still pending, but **no obvious critical bioactivities** have been observed. *In an in-depth risk assessment study, the screen battery would be expanded at this point also to include key experimental data on selected receptors, enzymes and transporters, and a broader coverage of*

potential target tissues. For the purpose of this demonstration study, other bioactivities, relevant to maternal toxicity, were considered to be absent.

3.3.3.1 Results on other bioactivities

The judgement of DNT hazard by NGRA is usually focused on potential effects of the test compound on the embryo or child. This differs from conventional assessments, as in animal models, there is a simultaneous exposure of the dam and the offspring, and so the relative toxicity can be judged. To add such information, and to cover some gaps of the assessment of DNT, DN-IMI is currently being evaluated in a broad general in vitro test battery. This is similar to batteries that have been used to assess adult systemic toxicity (e.g. in OECD IATA case studies) and it comprises cell stress ToxProfiler assays (by Toxys), CALUX nuclear receptor and endocrine disruptor assays (by BDS), additional cytotoxicity assays in primary human hepatocytes, and transcriptome profiling in primary human hepatocytes and LUHMES cells. The currently available data do not reveal any critical bioactivities. Details will become available at a later time point.

Supporting documents in subfolder B011_02 in Annex I

- RPTEC resazurin reduction : RPTEC resazurin reduction.xlsx
- DNT-IVB results.pdf (Including Figures 1 for UKN3+4 and Figure 2 for UKN2+5)
- OECD GD377.pdf
- Blum et al. 2023.pdf

3.4 In vitro biokinetics (BB012_01)

3.4.1 Summary

No corrections/adjustment are required, based on the physchem properties of the compound and the results of the VIVD model

3.4.2 Result

Using the VIVD model (developed by Certara; recently exemplified and described e.g. in Magel et al., 2024) the DN-IMI distribution within the cell culture dishes was calculated. The results showed neither accumulation within any compartment of the cell nor binding to cell culture plastic. From the physico-chemical properties of the compound it is not assumed that the compound binds to plastic or accumulates within cells. The predicted target lies on the outer surface of the cell membrane. Based on the results from the VIVD model, no correction is needed. The modelling was performed assuming a nominal concentration of 1 µM, the calculated free fraction relevant for triggering the nAChR was 0.87 µM. Modelled values can be found in Annex I The model scaling is linear, so that in general the free concentrations are considered to be within a ≤15% deviation from nominal concentrations.

Supporting documents in subfolder B012_01 in Annex I

- Neonicotinoids SIVA(1) : Neonicotinoids_SIVA(1).xlsx
- Magel et al. 2024.pdf

3.5 Integration of initial hazard and bioactivity data (BB013_01)

3.5.1 Summary

The results obtained so far indicate no cytotoxicity or experimentally-measured bioactivity up to a highest test concentration of 20-100 µM (see 3.3.3.1). More data needs to be generated to

follow up on the generated alert on the nAChR. Using information from the ADME and exposure pillars: we assume that expected internal exposures may reach low nM levels. Thus, bioactivities have been screened here up to a range that is 1000x higher than the expected concentrations (in brain or other tissues).

General note: In a regulatory safety assessment this ASPA building block is one of the most critical steps. Here, confidence must be reached that any significant effect on any toxicologically relevant process would have been identified by the panel of methods used. Such a 'full toxicological coverage' is a challenging goal. This is not a particular problem of ASPA, but of any NGRA approach. It is likely (highly probable) that there will be gaps in this case study, or any other that is being run with current methodology and a moderate investment of resources. A discussion of potential and/or likely gaps does not decrease regulatory uncertainty, but it may give better estimates of residual risk. For studies with regulatory ambitions, the discussion of toxicological coverage may be inserted here, in 3.13 and/or at the end of the assessment

3.5.2 Result

The QSAR predictions and in-silico docking models predict as a target the nAChR. None of the test methods investigated the response of the nAChR so far. The nAChR is a target of several known toxicants. The modulation of its activity needs to be verified. Additional new-approach methodologies (NAMs) need to be used to follow up on this alert.

3.6 Derive Point-of-Departure estimates (BB014_01)

3.6.1 Summary

No PoD can be derived so far

3.6.2 Result

From the current dataset no PoD could be derived, since data on a relevant lowest observed adverse effect concentration are missing.

3.7 Is a refinement of the POD(s) needed? (DP10EF_01)

3.7.1 Summary

A PoD has not yet been identified. A potential target of toxicological concern has been identified (chapter 3.1.2.1.). The target interaction has to be studied and quantified.

DECISION: YES

3.7.2 Justification

The toxicological-relevant bioactivity needs to be further explored, since no PoD has been derived from tier I (high-throughput) assays.

3.8 Specific toxicological alerts identified? AOPs triggered? (DP11EF_01)

3.8.1 Summary

A putative AOP for nAChR activation has been published (Grillberger et al., 2023). It needs to be studied, if its activation through DN-IMI occurs, and at which concentration.

DECISION: YES

3.8.2 Justification

Potential targets of DN-IMI have been identified (nAChR), and their toxicological relevance is known. A putative AOP for nAChR activation is available (Figure 4).

Figure 4 putative AOP for nAChR activation (adapted from Grillberger et al. 2023). Putative AOP (adverse outcome pathway) linking nAChR binding to potential adverse outcome related to DNT. The AOP is based on the assumed mode of action of nicotine, which might apply also to certain neonicotinoids and their metabolites. KE3 might be triggered via KE1 either directly or via KE2. At present, KE3 and the adjacent key event relationships are the most uncertain elements of the putative AOP. More information on these processes is necessary. MD: molecular dynamics; MIE: molecular initiating event; KE: key event; AO: adverse outcome; MEA: microelectrode array (PMID 37685977).

3.9 Generate medium-throughput in vitro toxicity data e.g., for relevant qAOPs or Defined Approaches (BB015_01)

3.9.1 Summary

The used approaches (BB013) didn't show any cytotoxicity or bioactivity, but in-silico alerts have been generated for nAChR. As follow-up, endpoint specific assays to test for nAChR activation have been used (calcium imaging, antagonist experiments and receptor desensitization).

These showed that **DN-IMI triggers nAChR activation with a PoD of 0.1 μM (7 $-\log(\text{M})$) (C.I. 30-300 nM; 7.52 – 6.52 $-\log(\text{M})$)**. When receptor desensitization was used as an endpoint, a PoD of 0.01 μM (8 $-\log(\text{M})$) was observed.

3.9.2 Result

Since there was an indication by the UPF QSAR model and SEA for nAChR binding, which was supported by the in-silico docking studies, we followed up by using functional assays to cover aspects of neuronal signaling. For this, a calcium imaging assay was performed, measuring the intracellular increase of calcium in LUHMES cells by a fluorescence indicator. After stimulation with DN-IMI a strong increase in intracellular calcium was observed with a PoD of 0.1 μM (Figure 1A in subfolder BB015_01 in Annex I).

To show the specificity of nAChR binding the effect of DN-IMI was blocked by specific antagonists (tubocurarine and mecamylamine). Both showed a concentration dependent decrease of the response evoked by DN-IMI, supporting a nAChR specific response (Figure 1B in subfolder BB015_01 in Annex I). The experiments were all controlled. Positive controls (nicotine) and negative controls showed the expected results. Antagonists worked at known potencies.

Receptor activation can lead to a desensitization of the receptor which makes it refractory during sensitive periods of development. To investigate the desensitization of the nAChR after DN-IMI treatment, LUHMES cells were pre-treated with DN-IMI and then stimulated with the physiological ligand of the nAChR, acetylcholine or a $\alpha 7$ specific agonist (ABT594). The pre-treatment decreased the response towards acetylcholine or ABT594 (Figure 1C in subfolder BB015_01 in Annex I) with a PoD of 0.01 μM . This indicates a receptor desensitization of the nAChR towards its physiological ligand which could lead to potential DNT effects.

To increase the plausibility of the obtained results from the DNT-IVB assay the parent compound IMI and nicotine were tested as well. Comparably to DN-IMI, IMI and nicotine did not generate any hit throughout the DNT-IVB, but they showed expected agonist effects in the Ca^{2+} assay (data shown in table 1 in subfolder BB015_01 in Annex I).

Each of the used functional endpoint-specific assays has their own experimental uncertainty, which can be expressed in the confidence intervals of the generated curves. The uncertainty for each assay of the DNT-IVB is described in Blum et al. 2023. Further uncertainties are introduced through the processing of raw image data into fluorescence values. From the fluorescence values of the negative control a threshold is calculated which determines a reactive cell. This threshold has its own uncertainty. The amount of reactive cells is expressed as the mean of at least 3 biological replicates with at least 3 technical replicates per biological replicate. This allows a state of the art definition of the data variability. The 95% confidence interval (C.I.) of the PoD of the Ca^{2+} data was about 0.5 \log_{10} units above and below the indicated value. This means that a PoD of 0.1 μM has a C.I. of 30 nM – 300 nM. These data need to be considered for the final assessment and BER calculation.

Supporting documents in Annex I

- DNT-IVB and calcium imaging results.pdf

3.10 In vitro biokinetics (BB016_01)

3.10.1 Summary

No corrections/adjustment are required due to the physico-chemical properties of the compound and the results of the VIVD model

3.10.2 Result

Using the VIVD model from Certara the distribution within the cell culture dishes was calculated. The modelling showed that assuming a nominal concentration of 0.1 μM (PoD), the calculated free concentration in the Ca^{2+} signaling assay was 87 nM. This is <15% different from the nominal value and was therefore neglected. Modelled values can be found in Annex III.

Supporting documents in subfolder BB012_01 in Annex I

- Neonicotinoids SIVA(1) : Neonicotinoids_SIVA(1).xlsx
- Magel et al. 2024.pdf

3.11 Integration of results (BB017_01)

3.11.1 Summary

Calcium imaging emerged as the most sensitive endpoint for LUHMES cells to detect effects of nicotine and DN-IMI.

3.11.2 Result

The obtained results indicate that the most sensitive endpoint is calcium imaging (PoD of 100 nM; C.I. 30-300 nM; 7.52 – 6.52 -log(M)). The PoD for the receptor desensitization for DN-IMI was even up to 10x lower.

3.12 Derive refined point of departure (BB041_01)

3.12.1 Summary

Concentration response and antagonist experiments point to a PoD of 0.1 μ M (C.I. 30-300 nM; 7.52 – 6.52 -log(M)). The PoD for the receptor desensitization by DN-IMI is 0.01 μ M. The overactivation of the receptor would be a clearly adverse effect, already known in toxicology (e.g. by nicotine). Therefore, this was chosen as most relevant PoD. Receptor desensitization over prolonged times has the potential to be adverse, but it is mechanistically less well documented for known toxicants. It remains an uncertainty of this ASPA evaluation to what extent the desensitization PoD is relevant to DNT (10 nM range; 8 -log(M)).

3.12.2 Result

Various functional endpoint-specific assays have been used to generate several PoDs for the bioactivity of DN-IMI. The assay for receptor desensitization, measuring the activity of the nAChR receptor to its physiological ligand after a pre-treatment with DN-IMI, resulted in a PoD of 0.01 μ M. The assay for concentration-dependent receptor activation, measuring acute receptor activity upon DN-IMI treatment resulted in a PoD of 0.1 μ M. This shows a range of the PoDs between 0.01 – 0.1 μ M. This range has an order of magnitude difference, introducing some uncertainty for the BER assessment.

3.13 PoD sufficiently refined? Confidence in PoD increased? (DP12EF_01)

3.13.1 Summary

The PoD is sufficiently refined, but it is associated with biological uncertainties.

DECISION: YES

3.13.2 Justification

The derived PoD is supported by receptor desensitization assays in the LUHMES cell line with a PoD of 0.01 μ M. Calcium imaging provided further evidence with a PoD at 0.1 μ M which is supported by the generated alerts from the QSAR models. Molecular docking studies and electrophysiological studies fully confirm the MIE assumed here.

Uncertainties concerning the PoD concern the experimental system used and the definition of the data interpretation procedure of the test method. Moreover, like in any AOP-based prediction, there is an uncertainty about the robustness, applicability and penetrance of the AOP. The latter point refers to the likelihood that the AO occurs, when the MIE is triggered. Such uncertainty needs to be categorized as medium-high. The applicability of the AOP is

suggested to be high, as it is well documented for nicotine. The confidence into penetrance would be increased, if KE closer to the AO were assessed. Such work is ongoing.

Note: AOPs play an important role in NGRA (also in ASPA). Their validation is a complex issue, and setting numbers to their uncertainty is extremely challenging. It is important not to confuse peer-review with validation, and to heed that validation/regulatory acceptance has its limits (applicability domain, purpose and sector of the validation etc.). A biological validation for the given context would increase confidence. It would also be highly beneficial if the AOP can be used in a quantitative way (which does not mean that a qAOP must exist). The quantifiability of AO, based on measurements of MIE or KE, will often depend on how distant the measured bioactivity is from the AO (the closer, the more reliable). These issues of NGRA will not be solved immediately. For ASPA reporting, this means that they need some discussion, concerning (in the context of the uncertainty evaluation).

3.14 Calculate appropriate HEC (BB025_01)

(see also chapter 4.4)

3.14.1 Summary

The most relevant HEC is suggested to be **20 µg/kg bw/day** (range: 6 µg/kg/day – 60 µg/kg/day) (based on receptor activation).

Uncertainty: The HEC may be as low as 2 µg/kg/day (considering receptor sensitization as relevant MIE)

3.14.2 Result

The PoD for receptor activation was 100 nM with a confidence interval from 30 nM to 300 nM. Using the PBK model (chapter 4.3) for backward modelling (IVIVE procedure), a concentration of 100 nM in fetal brain would correspond to a maternal daily exposure of 20 µg/kg bw. Considering the confidence interval of the PoD, the HEC would be 6 µg/kg/day – 60 µg/kg/day.

If the data for receptor desensitization is considered, then the PoD is 10 nM. The HEC would be 2 µg/kg/day

4. ADME

Disclaimer: Note that the points in chapter 4 refer to ASPA version V2.1 before the workshop reported here. The ADME chapter has been strongly revised (tiering; clear criteria for information gathering; separate consideration of metabolite formation). Chapter 4.3 (*of the present version*) will be converted into a series of detailed activities, separated by decision points (*in future ASPA versions*). Here, the relevant information was added in the single 4.2 building block of the present version.

4.1 Compound mainly cleared by metabolism? (DP05EF_01)

4.1.1 Summary

DN-IMI is not cleared by metabolism. The metabolism in hepatocytes was below the limit of quantification. For PBK modelling, therefore a clearance of 1.4 mL/min/kg bw, corresponding to passive renal clearance, is assumed.

DECISION: NO

4.1.2 Justification

In clearance studies conducted with DN-IMI in hepatocyte cultures, the measured in vitro intrinsic clearance was <0.143 ml/min/ 10^6 cells (i.e. below the limit of quantitation of the assay). N.B.: The positive control compounds ketoprofen and prednisolone had measured intrinsic clearance values of 4.4 and 0.38, ml/min/ 10^6 cells in the same experiment (data not shown).

In the absence of any further information, it is assumed that DN-IMI is not metabolized in the liver, and that it is mainly cleared via the kidneys. Further data are given below (chapter 4.3).

4.2 Are ADME properties known? (DP03EF_01)

Disclaimer: In the final ASPA version, this decision point is preceded by a task to summarize the known ADME properties. Such information is provided here in the justification of the decision.

4.2.1 Summary

Basic ADME properties are known (see below)

DECISION: YES

4.2.2 Justification

Metabolic clearance: none; *ECCS-class:* 4 (renal clearance)

Fraction absorbed: 0.64 ; *Blood/plasma ratio:* 0.76

Renal clearance: Renal clearance for DN-IMI was assumed to be governed only by passive processes, with both filtration and passive reabsorption being accounted for. A clearance of 3.42 L/h (0.78 mL/min/kg; 1.15 L/kg bw/day), corresponding to passive renal clearance (at a plasma f_u of 0.84) is assumed. Passive permeability was scaled from the predicted permeability in the intestine (P_{eff} $0.37 \cdot 10^{-4}$ cm/s) accounting for the surface area of the proximal tubules in the kidney. *Note: There was no alert concerning transport effects, but this may be investigated into some more depth. Also, a sensitivity analysis could be performed to see what difference this would make for the overall outcome of the evaluation.*

Plasma half-life: $T_{1/2}$ would be about 11 h with a volume of distribution (V_D) of 0.79 L/kg (as assumed in the PBK model), assuming that the toxicokinetics are described with a one compartment model.

Background on renal clearance: The PBK model was developed using an analogue approach whereby the model choices for the DN-IMI PBK model were informed using a model developed for atenolol, a compound with similar physicochemical features as DN-IMI. The atenolol model was able to recapitulate observed human pharmacokinetics. The renal CL for atenolol includes a component of active secretion, which was entered into the model using reported transporter kinetic data (Yin et al. 2015). In the absence of equivalent data for DN-IMI, no active secretion component was included for this compound. If active secretion does occur for DN-IMI this would result in a lower exposure of DN-IMI in the body.

PBK model(s): A general PBK model has been established and run with a simulation of 100 individuals (50% female). In an exemplary figure, concentration-time data are provided for daily oral dosing (16 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) for the plasma and brain compartments in annex II. Moreover, a model has been developed for pregnant women, incorporating also fetal compartments. Exemplary time concentration curves for daily repeated dosing of mothers with 16 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ are shown for fetal and maternal brain and plasma in figure 5. A documentation of the model is found in annex II. **Note that the model scales linearly** over a large range, i.e. doses that are 10-fold or 100-fold lower would correspondingly result into 10x or 100x lower internal exposures. For lack of experimental data for DN-IMI, the model has been fitted to data on atenolol, as described earlier (OECD, 2022, case study on imidacloprid in annex III)

Figure 5 Physiology-based kinetic (PBK) modeling of DN-IMI in pregnant women and their fetus.

(A) The systemic exposure following an oral dose of 0.016 mg DN-IMI/kg body weight, given every 24 h to 100 individuals (aged 18-45; 100% female) with randomly assigned phenotypic and genotypic properties typical for a caucasian Northern European population is shown. The predicted mean plasma concentrations of DN-IMI (green line) are shown with the 5th and 95th

percentiles of the population (dashed lines). The predicted mean brain concentrations of DN-IMI (light blue) are shown with the 5th and 95th percentiles of the population (dashed lines). (B) The mean plasma (dark blue left) and brain (dark blue right) concentrations of DN-IMI following multiple oral exposures of 0.016 mg DN-IMI/kg body weight, given every 24 h intervals to 100 individuals (aged 18-45; 100% female) with randomly assigned phenotypic and genotypic properties typical for a caucasian Northern European population for their foetuses are shown.

Background information on endogenous formation of DN-IMI in vertebrates: After imidacloprid exposure DN-IMI has been reported to be formed in the liver of rats and excreted into the faeces. There are some estimates that about 2% of imidacloprid may be transformed to DN-IMI, but the experimental basis for this is associated with high uncertainties. There are indications that DN-IMI was the major imidacloprid metabolite after incubation with human liver microsomes. There is also scientific research suggesting that aldehyde oxidase may be involved in the formation. Often independent confirmations for such work are missing. (See details in the background document ‘[DN-IMI_BB002_data.pdf](#)’ in annex II.)

4.3 Derive estimates of relevant test concentrations (BB008_01)

4.3.1 Summary

Based on plasma levels and brain levels expected in humans (mother and fetus), it is suggested to test DN-IMI at least up to the concentration of 10 μM (in the absence of any other information). **Maximal maternal brain concentrations: 7.1, 3.0, 0.06 nM; Maximal fetal brain concentrations: 7.8, 3.3, 0.06 nM in ES1, ES2, ES3** (exposure scenarios as in chapter 5)

4.3.2 Result

The **PBK model for pregnant women and their fetuses was run with an assumed exposure of 1.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ body weight/day**. This exposure marks the maximal environmental exposure (E_{max} of the highest scenario; ES1). The PBK modelling data suggest peak **fetal brain concentrations of 7.9 +/- 1.8 nM** (mean +/- SD), with a similar range reached in mothers. Plasma levels were in the same order of magnitude, but about 30% lower. [Note that the model scales linearly with the exposure dose and the data shown in Fig. 5 are for 10x higher doses.]

It was assumed here that testing should be performed at concentrations that are up to 1000 x higher, considering the uncertainties of exposure estimates, PBK modelling, hazard testing, and the exposure from short term test readouts to prolonged human exposure. Therefore, a highest test concentration of at least 10 μM is suggested here.

Supporting documents subfolder BB008_01 in Annex II

- DN-IMI Supplement PBK model figure.pdf
- DN-IMI Table 1 Supplements Annex II.docx
- Full documentation of the PBK model, of its setup and of the model output is found in the file ‘DN-IMI PBK model.pdf’. Note that this is an update (some altered data) of an older version found in the annex part of <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18279604>.
- DN-IMI_BB002_data.pdf

4.4 Translate 'HEC' into external human dose (BB043_01)

Disclaimer: the terminology has been adapted during optimization of ASPA. In chapter 3.14, the relevant hazard PoDs have been used in an IVIVE procedure to determine the 'external human dose leading to such internal concentrations'. This is now termed the HUMAN EQUIVALENT DOSE (HED) in new workflows (Leist et al., 2026)

4.4.1 Summary

The HED is **20 µg/kg bw/day**, with a range of 2 µg/kg/day – 60 µg/kg/day.

4.4.2 Result

The PoD for receptor activation was 100 nM with a confidence interval from 30 nM to 300 nM. Using the PBK model (chapter 4.3) for backward modelling (IVIVE procedure), a concentration of 100 nM in fetal brain would correspond to a maternal daily exposure of 20 µg/kg bw. Considering the confidence interval of the PoD, the hEC would be 6 µg/kg/day – 60 µg/kg/day.

If the data for receptor desensitization is considered, then the PoD is 10 nM. The HED would in this case be 2 µg/kg/day

4.5 Compare hazard and exposure reference value (BB026_01)

4.5.1 Summary

Two variants of the bioactivity-exposure relations (BER) and the margin of exposure (MoE) have been calculated. **There is only a small ratio of about 13 (ES1)**, or only a ratio of 1.3 (most conservative approach) between the toxicity threshold (HED) and the maximal exposure. For ES2, the ratio is about 31 and **for ES3, the ratio is 1690** (not considering desensitization).

4.5.2 Result

Hazard and exposure data can be compared in two ways (see below). Note that details on exposure data have been reported in chapter 5.

4.5.2.1 Variant 1: Comparison of bioactivity with internal exposure (iE) data

A PBK model (chapter 4.2) was used in the forward modelling mode to predict internal exposure from external exposure. Modelling was performed for the plasma and brain concentrations of 100 pregnant women and their fetuses (at gestational week (GW) = 30):

Note: The ratio of internal exposure and (toxicologically relevant) bioactivity is a complex measure, as both the numerator and denominator have uncertainties that should be perpetuated into the final ratio. Some considerations are noted below for ES1 (not for ES2 and ES3), in a highly simplified form. More sophisticated procedures have been developed and used elsewhere. They are not used and exemplified here, as this is not a core element required to understand ASPA. However, ASPA guidance stipulates the use of best practices in the field.

ES1: Assuming the maximal daily exposure value of 1.6 µg/kg DN-IMI, a peak brain concentration of 7.9 nM was predicted (with up and down variations of up to 40%). This data was compared to the bioactivity data (PoD) of 100 nM by forming the internal bioactivity-exposure ratio (iBER): 12.7.

Note: If receptor desensitization (10 nM) was considered the most relevant PoD, the iBER would be 1.3. Here, we have argued that the AOP for this PoD is of low reliability and it has

therefore not been considered. This is an example that not any bioactivity qualifies for the iBER. However, the span from 1.3 to 12.7 must be considered an uncertainty range for the iBER, with a need to further investigate how receptor desensitization translates to an adverse outcome.

The background to this is that the effects on nAChR are used, along the AOP suggested for nicotine, concerning DNT. Typical nicotine effects in vivo are associated with tremors, hyperactivity and some morphological changes (e.g. in nucleus accumbens) at high doses (Roy et al., 2002). This may be interpreted rather as sign of over-activation than a sign of desensitization (but more data would be useful). Therefore, **we used here the data on DN-IMI acting as agonist on the nAChR as the most relevant PoD** (and not the more potent effect on desensitization).

With relation to hazard uncertainty, it should also be noted that no proof has been obtained that the AOP, assumed here, is always resulting in an AO, once the MIE is triggered. The analogy to nicotine provides plausibility, but this would be strengthened by data on more proximal key events (closer to the AO).

Based on exposure scenario ES2, the internal C_{max} (fetal brain) would be 3.3 nM. The iBER would then be 30.5 (not considering desensitization).

Based on exposure scenario ES3, the internal C_{max} (fetal brain) would be 0.06 nM. The iBER would then be 1690 (not considering desensitization)

Note that here, instead of a simple ratio formation of PoD and iE, also advanced modelling tools may be used that work with a data distribution around the PoD and a distribution around the internal exposure and then 'divide' the two distributions to obtain distribution data for the iBER (e.g. by Monte Carlo sampling).

4.5.2.2 Variant 2: Comparison of threshold dose predictions (HED) with external exposure data

A PBK model (4.5.2.1) was used in the reverse modelling mode to predict the HED from in vitro PoDs (see chapter 3.14).

The PoD for receptor activation was 100 nM with a confidence interval from 30 nM to 300 nM. The PBK model (chapter 4.2), used for backward modelling (IVIVE procedure), predicted that a concentration of 100 nM in fetal brain would correspond to a maternal daily exposure of 20 µg/kg bw.

Considering the confidence interval of the PoD, the hEC would be 6 µg/kg/day – 60 µg/kg/day. [If the data for receptor desensitization is considered, then the PoD is 10 nM. The hEC would be 2 µg/kg/day]. This data was compared to the maximal external exposure (ES1) of 1.6 µg/kg/day by forming the external HED-exposure ratio: 12.7. For the PoD of receptor desensitization (10 nM), this ratio is 1.3. **The span from 1.3 to 12.7 gives the rough uncertainty range.** *If desired, this may be modelled also by a ratio of probability distributions.*

As for variant 1, the ratio for ES2 would be 31 and for ES3 it would be 1690

4.5.2.3 Margin of exposure (MoE)

The margin of exposure may be useful in some contexts of data discussion, especially, when its uncertainty range is modelled. In ES3 (realistic for European population), the MoE is about 1700.

If ES1 is considered (worst case), there is hardly any margin: the exposure leading to hazard would differ from the maximal nutritional exposure only by a factor of 13.

5. Exposure

5.1 Map the uses of the substance (BB020_01)

5.1.1 Summary

The compound is not in commercial use. It is generated in the environment from imidacloprid. The major route of and source of exposure is through contaminated food. The target population is assumed (for demonstration purposes of this case study) to be the **general consumer in a country with high use of imidacloprid** (compound not banned), which may be the situation in Spain 15 years ago, or the present situation in countries like Brazil, China or Jordan. The exposure estimates are indirect (see next paragraph), as there are no standard monitoring programs for DN-IMI (DN-IMI is not a pesticide product, but a secondary product formed within crops). The potential endogenous formation of DN-IMI from ingested imidacloprid is neglected here (as such metabolism data have high uncertainties).

The approach taken here is a two-step process:

- step-I, **information on the exposure to the parent compound (imidacloprid) is used as reference point;**
- step-II, it is assumed that the DN-IMI concentrations in food are a certain (on average constant) fraction of the amount of IMI. Here, it is **assumed that DN-IMI concentrations amount to 2% of the imidacloprid levels.**

5.1.2 Result

Historical and geographic overview of use:

Up to 15 years ago, imidacloprid has been one of the most used pesticides world-wide. The global production in 2010 was about 20.000 tons. For instance, in Spain it was used on citrus and vegetable crops in the tons/year range for several single crops. Since 2013, its use drastically fell in the EU (bans mainly for reasons of bee protection). Use patterns and residue levels in food have been documented in EFSA reports (see [annex III](#)), referring to exposure of the European population. Several recent publications are also available on monitoring in other countries.

Concerning the global situation at present, it is important that imidacloprid continues to be used in many Asian and South American countries to the present day. For instance, in Brazil, imidacloprid use in recent years was roughly in the 2000 tons range. Imidacloprid is one of the most frequently detected pesticides in Brazilian food monitoring programs, with hundreds of positive samples in recent national surveys. The Brazilian PARA program (ANVISA), in its 2017–2018 cycle (reported 2019), analyzed 4,616 food samples and searched for up to 270

active ingredients. In this dataset imidacloprid was the single most frequently detected pesticide, with 713 detections among the samples. Imidacloprid is described as one of the ten most commercialized pesticides in Brazil and a leading insecticide found in national food residue monitoring, which explains its prominence in PARA detections. **Imidacloprid residues are regularly detected in both citrus, pome fruits and several vegetables (like egg plants)**, with most samples below MRLs but a relevant minority exceeding legal limits or showing multiple residues.

Brazil is not an exceptional example. There is a large number of publications from China and many other countries. For instance, analytical data from Jordan suggest a similar picture: imidacloprid in 300 vegetable and fruit samples obtained from 15 major wholesalers in four regions of Amman, Jordan's capital city, were analyzed. **Among the examined samples, 40 % were found to be contaminated with imidacloprid residues.** Imidacloprid levels in different edible fruits and vegetables ranged from less than the Limit of Quantification to 0.4 mg kg⁻¹. **Eggplants and apples exhibited the highest average values (0.40 and 0.25 mg kg⁻¹, respectively).** Overall, 25 samples (8.3 %) exceeded the Codex maximum residue limit (MRL) for imidacloprid. Moreover, 8 out of the 300 samples (2.7 %) exceeded the MRL established by the Pest Management Regulatory Agency (PMRA). Notably, the fruits of eggplant and apple contained the highest residual levels (1.30 and 0.83 mg kg⁻¹, respectively), markedly exceeding the CODEX and PMRA MRLs. Additionally, the maximum detected imidacloprid residue concentration in bananas (0.25 mg kg⁻¹) was 500 % higher than the CODEX MRLs.

These data indicate that in some populations (e.g. in the European Union), there may be very low nutritional exposures, but in some sub-populations of other countries (in particular, in individuals with uncommon nutritional patterns, there may be clearly higher levels than on average (see details in the background document '[DN-IMI_BB002_data_V2.pdf](#)' in annex III).

Relation of DN-IMI to imidacloprid residues

DN-IMI can be produced in the environment from its parent compound imidacloprid. It is not produced for any commercial use. Rather, DN-IMI is an environmental degradation product of the pesticide imidacloprid. It may be found in soil or plants, following a treatment with imidacloprid. It is generated by metabolic processes (in plants or soil bacteria), possibly also by abiotic processes. DN-IMI can be taken up as food contaminant through the oral route from 'contaminated' fruit or vegetable. The target population is the consumer. Operators or factory workers are likely not exposed to DN-IMI. Therefore: occupational exposures during production (including packaging and transport or for operators (applying the pesticide to crops) have not been considered here.

Supporting documents in Annex III

- EFSA (2021). The 2019 European Union report on pesticide residues in food. *EFSA Journal* 19, e06491. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6491>
- EFSA (2020). The 2018 European Union report on pesticide residues in food. *EFSA Journal* 18, 6057. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6057>
- EFSA Journal - 2019 - - Review of the existing maximum residue levels for imidacloprid according to Article 12 of : EFSA Journal - 2019 - - Review of the existing maximum residue levels for imidacloprid according to Article 12 of.pdf
- EFSA Journal - 2013 - - Scientific Opinion on the developmental neurotoxicity potential of acetamiprid and imidacloprid : EFSA Journal - 2013 - - Scientific Opinion on the developmental neurotoxicity potential of acetamiprid and imidacloprid.pdf

- Final addendum DAR Imidacloprid March 2008 : Final addendum DAR Imidacloprid March 2008.pdf
- The 2023 European union report on pesticide residues in food : The 2023 European union report on pesticide residues in food.pdf
- DN-IMI_BB002_data_V2.pdf
- Loser et al. 2021a-supplement (PMID33778899)
- Loser et al., 2021b (PMID34628512)
- OECD IATA case study 366 imidacloprid (2022) with annex.pdf; OECD case study on IMI (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18279604>)
- Risk characterization document dietary and drinking water exposure EPA 2006.pdf

5.2 Screen possible exposure scenarios (BB021_01)

5.2.1 Summary

The exposure to the parent compound (imidacloprid) has been repeatedly evaluated and documented in the publicly available literature. Here, in exposure scenario 1 (ES1: worst case level) the maximal exposure levels of general consumers to **imidacloprid have been set to 80 µg/kg/day. A fraction of 2% (1.6 µg/kg/day) was assumed here for exposure to DN-IMI.**

In another exposure scenarios (ES2), an $E_{\max 2}$ of **0.66 µg/kg bw/day** (660 ng/kg/day; 2.4-fold lower than $E_{\max 1}$) has been assumed.

In ES3, an $E_{\max 3}$ of **0.012 µg/kg bw/day** (12 ng/kg/day; 133-fold lower than $E_{\max 1}$) has been assumed

5.2.2 Result

ASPA background: For risk assessment case studies in defined regulatory contexts, here a screen would be performed for possible exposure scenarios. This would involve systematically identifying and evaluating situations where individuals might come into contact with a substance. Data on e.g. sources, pathways, volume distribution, target populations (geography, time, special age or professional characteristics, etc.), would be collected and documented. **Here, a simplified approach has been taken, as the major purpose of the study is identification of the hazard of an environmental compound for which exposure data are limited.**

Assumptions and calculations leading to the maximal exposure estimates (E_{\max}). DN-IMI can be produced by plants or by soil bacteria from its parent compound imidacloprid. DN-IMI can therefore be taken up as a food contaminant through the oral route. It was assumed here that intake would be 2% of the intake of imidacloprid (see background documents).

For exposure scenario 3 (ES3, mild case), a realistic exposure applying to the European population was chosen. The starting point was European consumer data that suggest that real exposure to imidacloprid is always below 1% of the ADI (EFSA, 2021); p. 50). The $E_{\max 3}$ was set to be 0.012 µg/kg bw/day (12 ng/kg/day). This is based on a maximal imidacloprid intake of 0.6 µg/kg bw/day (corresponding to 1% ADI; imidacloprid ADI = 60 µg/kg/day). This was multiplied by 0.02 (corresponding to a DN-IMI fraction of 2%).

For exposure scenario 2 (ES2), an anchoring to the imidacloprid ADI (60 µg/kg/day) was used. Documents submitted for regulatory evaluation (European Commission 2006, 2008) suggest that DN-IMI is 2.2 % of imidacloprid. Furthermore, we assumed that the realistic intake

of imidacloprid would never exceed 50% of the ADI. In this case the $E_{\max 2}$ would be $30 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day} \times 0.022 = 0.66 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$ ($660 \text{ ng}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$). This value is about 2.4-fold lower than the here assumed $1.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$ ($1600 \text{ ng}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$) for $E_{\max 1}$.

For exposure scenario 1 (ES1, worst case), an exposure of $1.6 \mu\text{g DN-IMI}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$ ($E_{\max 1}$) was assumed, as this assumption has been used in earlier studies and in an OECD case study on imidacloprid/DN-IMI (Loser et al., 2021b; Loser et al., 2021a); OECD 2022; references collected in annex III). This value is about 133-fold higher than the here assumed $0.012 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$ ($12 \text{ ng}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$) for $E_{\max 3}$.

The basic assumptions to arrive at ES1 were as follows: the acute reference dose (ARfD) currently in use by EFSA for imidacloprid ($80 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$) was used as upper intake limit; it was assumed that a fraction of 2% of this exposure is DN-IMI. *The use of the ARfD as anchoring point must be considered a high end of the worst case, but it may be biologically justified in the case of a potential DNT hazard.* For developmental toxicity, it is known that there are highly defined windows of sensitivity during pregnancy, so that short high exposures during such time periods may have particular effects (well-documented for thalidomide). As a background, it may be noted that an older ARfD (used worldwide (FAO/WHO) was at even higher levels ($400 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$). Moreover, data from the Californian EPA (1994-1998) suggest that exposures up to a high percentage (30-80%) of the ARfD have been reached in US subpopulations, when the 95th percentile of exposure was considered.

Uncertainties of exposure assumptions. Anchoring to reference doses, as opposed to experimentally-determined exposures has limitations. This was buffered by the choice of three different ES. The major uncertainty is the choice of the study population. Depending on the uses of imidacloprid and the actual regulations and their enforcements, different exposure scenarios are possible over geographies and times. The ES1 – ES2 – ES3 assumptions span a wide range of these.

It needs to be mentioned that **endogenous formation** of DN-IMI (by human metabolism) may add to the amount of ingested DN-IMI. As there are no reliable data on this (and the contribution was judged to be low), this feature of aggregated exposure has not been considered here.

Since DN-IMI may be formed in animals used for meat production, and as imidacloprid may also be found in feed, there may be some level of **DN-IMI exposure through meat**. As the data on this is not reliable (and are likely very low), this additional additional exposure route has been neglected. It also needs to be mentioned that use of imidacloprid changes over time. This also applies to residue levels on imported food. This can lead to some variation of estimated intakes (compare e.g. the reports of EFSA 2020 and EFSA 2021)

5.3 Prioritize routes of exposure (BB040_01)

5.3.1 Summary

The route of exposure is oral intake as a food contaminant. Other routes of exposure were excluded. The ADME module assumed a bioavailability of 100%.

5.3.2 Result

In a detailed risk assessment study, this building block requires an estimate of the efficiency of absorption for all potential exposure routes, identified as relevant for the scenarios in 5.2. Estimates would be based on compound ADME properties (experimental and/or predicted).

The most significant/relevant exposure routes would be identified and further pursued. If necessary, aggregate exposure would be considered.

5.4 Estimate highest exposure for relevant routes and sources (BB022_01)

5.4.1 Summary

In ES1, a maximal **daily intake of 0.0016 mg/kg body weight for DN-IMI** was assumed (= 1.6 µg DN-IMI/kg/day). This conclusion is based on maximal imidacloprid exposures of 160 µg/kg/day and an assumption that the DN-IMI levels were up to 1% of the imidacloprid levels (see 5.3)

In ES2 an **E_{max2} of 0.66 µg/kg bw/day** has been assumed.

In ES3, an **E_{max3} of 0.012 µg/kg bw/day** has been assumed

Result

The highest external exposure was estimated for a population of consumers (oral route; intake as food contaminant) that reside in a world area with high imidacloprid usage. This would correspond to the situation as in Europe 15 years ago (before imidacloprid use was severely restricted). This exposure situation may apply at present to many regions in Asia and South America. One should add here that the ES1 assumes also special worst case conditions in such a population. ES2 is more intermediate, and ES3 may be realistic worse case for present consumers in Europe.

ES calculations were as detailed in 5.2.2

Uncertainty considerations: The above data were used as estimate to calculate maximal internal exposure levels (see chapter 4). Such data were used to inform on the highest test concentrations for hazard testing. In reality, the DN-IMI exposure may be considerably lower than 1.6 µg/kg/day for most consumers (ES1). This was, however, not relevant for the hazard testing, as the test concentrations used anyway explored lower concentrations. In addition, many NAMs used a 1000-fold excess of the predicted maximal internal concentration, to provide a safety margin. Concerning the overall assessment, the uncertainty of the exposure had no impact on the estimated human equivalent dose. The latter was not based on any assumptions used for exposure. It is only based on hazard data (obtained ab initio) and ADME modelling, using state of the art parametrization of the PBK model: the HED was then obtained by IVIVE from the hazard testing PoD. However, it needs to be noted that the uncertainty of exposure estimates adds uncertainty to the bioactivity-exposure relationship (discussed in the respective chapter)

Supporting documents

See in subfolder B020_01 in Annex III

5.5 Prioritize sources of exposure (BB041_01)

5.5.1 Summary

Oral intake was considered as only exposure route

5.5.2 Result

The only relevant route of exposure is through oral intake as a food contaminant. See for further details in 5.1-5.4. Rodent studies have indicated that DN-IMI (2% range) may be formed from

imidacloprid (and be excreted in the intestine). The data have high uncertainties. Therefore, especially considering human metabolism. Therefore, endogenous formation of DN-IMI has not been considered here.

5.6 Is the exposure estimate acceptable and of sufficient quality? (DP14EF_01)

5.6.1 Summary

The exposure prediction, and the underlying assumptions, have been considered reliable for the purpose of this study.

DECISION: YES

5.6.2 Justification

The exposure data for imidacloprid are based on several EFSA reports ([annex III](#)). The assumption of a DN-IMI content of 2% is in line with earlier studies and estimates ([annex III](#)). It may be classified as ‘realistic worst case’ (see 5.3 for uncertainty discussion).

6. Integration

6.1 Compare hazard and exposure reference values (BB026_01)

Disclaimer: This building block depends on earlier decisions taken in ASPA assist. Depending on the flow of information (as pertinent to the present assessment), this task has already been performed in **chapter 4.5 (see details there)**. The summary is repeated here.

6.1.1 Summary

The bioactivity-exposure relations (BER, two variants) and the margin of exposure (MoE) have been calculated. For exposure scenario 3 (ES3) there is a large MoE and accordingly an iBER of about 1700. If more extreme (worst case scenarios are considered, the MoE (or iBER) are in the range of 31 or 13.

The HED is 20 µg/kg bw/day, with a range of 2 µg/kg/day – 60 µg/kg/day

6.2 Is margin of exposure sufficient (DP19EF_01)

6.2.1 Summary

In a classical risk assessment, a MoE of 13 or below (ES1) would not suggest safe use of a substance. Exposure scenarios in which this is the case would need to be avoided. **A MoE > 1000 (here: about 1700 for ES3) would appear rather safe.**

6.2.2 Justification

This issue would need major attention and careful discussion in the reporting. The question on the margin of exposure (MoE) is placed within the ASPA to stimulate feedback and discussion on the data, the underlying assumptions and the uncertainties. The handling depends on exact use cases, and scenarios.

In case the MoE is considered (too) low, then exposure, hazard or ADME data would need re-consideration. This may require extra efforts that lead to an improvement in scope, quality and/or robustness. If this is unlikely to change the outcome, (or if it does not change the outcome), measures to limit exposure would need to be considered.

In the present case study, a starting point would be to obtain a more solid database on DN-IMI exposure through food. It also is important to obtain further information on actual brain concentrations, and finally, the later KE of the AOP needs to be confirmed (and quantified) experimentally to increase the robustness of the assessment.

7. Reporting

At this stage, the ASPA-assist2.1 output ends and suggests the addition of personal or public notes for further steps, follow-ups, etc.

A risk assessment report can be generated by specialists, based on the material provided here. This is independent of the decision taken in decision point DP19 (chapter 6.2). However, further actions, follow-up or risk management would depend on the MoE. Such issues require still a careful weight-of-evidence (WoE) approach and go beyond the initial scope of ASPA. For instance, available hazard data on imidacloprid may be used as a potential reference point (Sheets et al., 2026; Sheets et al., 2016)

8. References and Annexes

(References are partly annotated; indications are added as to where they may be retrieved, if not available as open access (e.g. via PubMed).

EFSA Journal - 2019 - - Review of the existing maximum residue levels for imidacloprid according to Article 12 of : EFSA Journal - 2019 - - Review of the existing maximum residue levels for imidacloprid according to Article 12 of.pdf

EFSA Journal - 2013 - - Scientific Opinion on the developmental neurotoxicity potential of acetamiprid and imidacloprid : EFSA Journal - 2013 - - Scientific Opinion on the developmental neurotoxicity potential of acetamiprid and imidacloprid.pdf

EFSA (2021). The 2019 European Union report on pesticide residues in food. *EFSA Journal* 19, e06491. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6491>

EFSA (2020). The 2018 European Union report on pesticide residues in food. *EFSA Journal* 18, 6057. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6057>

The 2023 European union report on pesticide residues in food : The 2023 European union report on pesticide residues in food.pdf

See the five references above in Annex III

Final addendum DAR Imidacloprid March 2008 : Final addendum DAR Imidacloprid March 2008.pdf

Grillberger, K., Cöllén, E., Trivisani, C. I. et al. (2023). Structural insights into neonicotinoids and n-unsubstituted metabolites on human nachrs by molecular docking, dynamics simulations, and calcium imaging. *Int J Mol Sci* 24, doi:10.3390/ijms241713170

Koshlukova SE (2006) Imidacloprid risk characterization document: dietary and drinking water exposure. Department of Pesticide Regulation, California Environmental Protection Agency. <https://www.cdpr.ca.gov/docs/risk/rcd/imidacloprid.pdf>. Accessed 17 May 2021 (*see in Annex III*)

Leist, M., Tangianu, S., Affourtit, F. et al. (2026). An alternative safety profiling algorithm (aspa) to transform next generation risk assessment into a structured and transparent process. *ALTEX* 43, 158-175. doi:10.14573/altex.2509081 (also in the zenodo repository with teh annexes)

Loser, D., Grillberger, K., Hinojosa, M. G. et al. (2021a). Acute effects of the imidacloprid metabolite desnitro-imidacloprid on human nach receptors relevant for neuronal signaling. *Arch Toxicol* 95, 3695-3716. doi:10.1007/s00204-021-03168-z

Loser, D., Hinojosa, M. G., Blum, J. et al. (2021b). Functional alterations by a subgroup of neonicotinoid pesticides in human dopaminergic neurons. *Arch Toxicol* 95, 2081-2107. doi:10.1007/s00204-021-03031-1

The Loser papers (2021a/b) include the PBK models for imidacloprid and DN-IMI and also the assumed exposure data. (found also in Annex III)

Magel et al., 2024 (PMID39768149)

Evaluation of picoxystrobin that was used for a general exemplification of ASPA principles in Leist et al., 2026)

OECD 2022. OECD case study on imidacloprid and DN-IMI (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18279604>)

The case study may be found on the OECD website, or (easier) via the zenodo link. It contains extensive documentation of the PBK model.

Sheets LP, Li AA, Minnema DJ, Collier RH, Creek MR, Peffer RC (2016). A critical review of neonicotinoid insecticides for developmental neurotoxicity. *Crit Rev Toxicol.*;46:153-90. doi: 10.3109/10408444.2015.1090948.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26513508/>

Comparison of five neonicotinoids for DNT effects: no consistent pattern pointing to DNT, no pattern similar to nicotine.

Sheets LP, Patel M, Zorrilla L, Bothe K (2026). Analysis of two guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity studies with imidacloprid to assist the interpretation of findings that impact global registrations. *Regul Toxicol Pharmacol.*;167:106040. doi: 10.1016/j.yrtph.2026.106040;

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0273230026000139?via%3Dihub>

Recent summary on two OECD compliant DNT studies on imidacloprid. Rare case of a confirmation study on a pesticide in wide-spread use

Annexes

All annexes (together with a publication file containing the full, high-resolution ASPA scheme, Leist 2026-supplement) are found under a single doi in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18849635>). The repository will contain an overview (excel sheet) together with zip-files for each annex.

High resolution overview of ASPA V2.1

(see next page)

